

REVIEW

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Green Belts: A Practical Approach for Environmental Sustainability

Bhupinder Dhir

Department of Chemistry, St. Stephens College, University of Delhi, Delhi, India

*Correspondence for materials should be addressed to BD (email: dhirb2021@gmail.com)

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Abstract

Green belts (GB) are the open vegetation zones existing near the urban and industrial set ups. They possess potential to clean environment. They act as sink for air pollutants and also aid in abatement of noise pollution. They also perform important functions such as climatic amelioration, biomass generation, adding to the aesthetic value of the area, and supporting regional biodiversity. The functioning of green belt area depends upon type of vegetation, topography of the area where it is developed and sources of pollution. A set of guidelines set by authorities need to be followed while developing green belt areas in specific zones. In today's era of environmental deterioration and climate change, concept of green belt has changed. The development of multifunctional green belt areas has gained momentum. These green belt areas not only assist in abatement of environmental pollution, maintenance of ecological balance, prevention of urban extension but also act as sources of recreation and employment. Therefore, green belts areas can prove beneficial in preventing environmental damage, maintenance of ecological sustainability and sustenance of life in future.

Keywords: Green belts; Aesthetic; Air pollution; Biodiversity; Shrubs; Trees; Noise**Introduction**

Intensive urbanization and industrialization have resulted in deterioration in environmental quality via addition of pollutants and wastes from various sources such as domestic areas and industrial units (Tayal et al., 2023; De and Das, 2024; Supriya et al., 2025; Meenatchi and Sathya, 2025). These contaminants prove a threat to the living organisms therefore, environmentalists/policy makers urged the need for development and maintenance of perennial green vegetation areas around the industrial zones, residential areas and mining zones (Taylor, 2019; Pourtaherian and Jaeger, 2022; Kirby and Scott, 2023; Kirby et al., 2023). Any naturally existing area, open space or wild areas that possess tree plantations or vegetation and exist around the urban areas or industrial set ups are referred to as Greenbelt (GB). The concept of Green Belt was developed in the late 19th century. It started with an idea of developing Garden Cities proposed by Ebenezer Howard in 1898. According to him these garden cities were supposed to be well-planned cities surrounded by greenbelts. The concept of creating greenbelt areas gained recognition in England after the Second World War (Sturzaker and Mell, 2016), and policies for developing planned cities with green belts were implemented (Han and Go, 2019). A campaign launched in 1930 with the name of Campaign to Protect Rural England (CPRE) proposed development of green areas that can provide protection against extensive development and urban extension (Pourtaherian and Jaeger, 2022). As per literature records, London and Sheffield were the two cities that developed Green Belt areas. The development of green belts areas was supported by both national policy and legislation. Green belt areas have effectively handled issues such as urban sprawl. At the same time they have also provided benefits to the society (Bishop et al., 2020; Kirby et al., 2023; Taylor, 2019; Pourtaherian and Jaeger, 2022). These areas establish a coordination between inhabited land, industrial hubs and agricultural zones.

In the late 19th century, greenbelt policies were framed with the objective of establishing these vegetated zones near the industrial sites only so as to remove pollution coming from these sources. But later, the greenbelt concept was reconsidered and reframed by policy makers to address the

serious issues such as massive environmental degradation, climate change and biodiversity loss. The present-day concept of Green Belt (GB) is based on holistic improvement of the areas which includes protection of natural resources, improvement in quality of environment by abatement of pollution (air and noise), restoring the quality of soil, prevention of land degradation, creation of recreational zones and employment avenues for the local people. Since the 1990s, a new generation of GBs have evolved which have been developed with the objectives of getting multiple benefits such as climate mitigation/adaptation, economic development, ecosystem services and regional recognition (Macdonald et al., 2021; Dockerill and Sturzaker 2020; Kirby et al., 2023).

Importance of green belt areas

Studies have shown that green belt areas have proven very effective in the abatement of environmental pollution existing in an area and maintenance of ecological balance of the region (Rao et al., 2004; Gupta et al., 2008; Islam et al., 2012; Obi et al., 2021; Kirby et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024). Many important roles can be assigned to green belt areas. Green belt areas bring improvement in air quality. Trees and vegetation present in the GB remove gases like carbon dioxide, trap particulate matter and help in purification of air. The air quality is also improved by release of oxygen. Green belt zones help in abatement of noise pollution. Trees present in the GB act as sound absorbers or sound barriers and mask the effect of sound coming from industrial set ups, vehicular traffic or mining operations. Studies have indicated that tree species such as *Polyalthia longifolia* and *Azadirachta indica* function as effective sound absorbers. The role of green belt areas in controlling soil erosion is also well known. Vegetation present in the green belts enrich soil with organic matter and contributes in improving soil quality status. The roots of trees and other plants bind/hold to soil particles and prevent soil erosion. Green belt areas manage water runoff. They retain water and prevent water runoffs. They prove useful in ground water infiltration and improve ground water recharge. These green zones are full of vegetation. Trees and other vegetation present in these areas provide habitat for animals and wildlife. Green belt areas enhance the beauty (aesthetic value) of the region. Ecological functions played by green belt areas include regulation of microclimate of a region by influencing temperature, moisture, and wind velocity. The green belt areas also act as shock absorbers or buffer zones. They also regulate the accidental spills/leakages of pollutants. Activities such as fishing, aquaculture and tourism in green belt areas provide employment opportunities for the local communities. Hence, these areas add to the socio-economic value of the region.

Approaches for developing green belt areas

Two types of approaches are followed for designing green belts.

- Source-oriented approach
- Receptor-oriented approach

Source-oriented approach is used in areas where a single source of pollution or contamination is located. The pollutants released from the source is tackled/treated. In this type, the pollution is mitigated at its origin and impact on surrounding areas is reduced.

Receptor-oriented approach is used in urban/industrial areas where multiple sources of pollution are present along with human settlements. The pollutants emitted from different sources can be treated effectively minimizing the impact of pollutants.

Source-oriented approach for green belt development is followed in areas having an industrial zone or a manufacturing plant. Receptor approach is adopted in industrial–urban mix areas with multiple sources of pollution.

Specifications for development/designing of green belt area

Certain specifications have been given by the government authorities for the development of green belt areas. According to the specifications, about 33% of the total site area is generally considered ideal for development of a green belt. According to the guideline, local species need to be planted. Plantations should be done in rows. Each row should alternate the previous one to prevent grazing and pollution dispersion. Plants should be grown with a spacing of 2 meters by 3 meters. Trees should be planted along the boundary in an arrangement in 2 to 10 rows each having a width of 2 to 3 meter. The green belt should consist of tall, evergreen trees planted along the boundary. The tree needs to be planted in a specific order with shorter trees (height less than 10 m) in the inner rows of the green belt, while tall trees (height more than 10 m) should be planted in the outer row. An additional row of avenue plantations can be done on either side of roads maintaining a distance of ten meters between trees.

The width of the green belt can vary and it depends upon the area where it has to be developed, sources of pollution, population density and many other factors (Gupta et al., 2008). The width and density of green belt should be adequate so as to provide protection against particulates and noise.

Vegetation used in green belt areas should follow a certain criterion. Tree species of height more than 5 meters and shrubs of height ranging between 1 to 1.5 m should be planted. Trees should have huge canopy areas but tree trunks should not have any foliage so that small shrubs can be planted in front and in between the tree spaces. Fast growing trees should be grown so that GB be developed in a short time span. Indigenous species of plants should be preferred as they show resistance to specific air pollutants and maintain regional ecological balance via soil and hydrology. The species will show better adaptability and produce optimum harvest on a sustained basis. Grasses should be cultivated as they stabilize the soil surface and contribute to organic enrichment of the soil. The pollution tolerant plant species should be used (Gopamma et al., 2022). Intermixing of trees and shrubs should be done so as to get high and uniform foliage density. The species used should be capable of enriching soil, through nitrogen fixation or decomposition of leaf litter. Members of Leguminaceae family such as *Leucaena leucocephala*, *Acacia farnesiana* can be used as they show good nitrogen fixing capacity. Tree/plant species which bear multiple uses should be chosen to get ecological and economic benefits. Example- Tree species such as *Populus*, *Eucalyptus*, *Acacia*, *Delonix*, *Azadirachta* offer multiple benefits. Besides improving air quality, they provide materials such as wood, medicines etc.

A list of pollution tolerant plants thus selected for the better Green Belt development in and around any industrial settlement (Table 1).

Table 1. Species of trees and shrubs suggested to be planted in green belt areas in India

Type of vegetation /species	Name of the species
Trees	<i>Acacia catechu</i> <i>Acacia nilotica</i> <i>Albizia lebbbeck</i> <i>Albizia amara</i> <i>Azadirachta indica</i> <i>Alstonia scholaris</i> <i>Terminalia arjuna</i> <i>Butea superba</i> <i>Syzygium cuminii</i> <i>Mangifera indica</i> <i>Ficus religiosa</i> <i>Delonix regia</i> <i>Pongamia pinnata</i> <i>Terminalia catappa</i> <i>Bauhinia acuminata</i> <i>Ficus benghalensis</i>
Shrubs	<i>Cassia fistula</i> <i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i> <i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> <i>Ricinus Communis</i> <i>Thevetia peruviana</i>
Herbs	<i>Lantana camara</i> <i>Tecoma stans</i> <i>Vernonia augustifolia</i> <i>Bougainvillea spectabilis</i> <i>Medicago sativa</i> <i>Phaseolus mungo</i> <i>Desmodium triflorum</i>
Grasses	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> <i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> <i>Saccharum spontaneum</i> <i>Cymbopogon fulvus</i> <i>Heteropogon contortus</i>

A top-down approach is followed by governments or large organizations for developing green belt areas. This approach results in quick establishment of large-scale green belt areas. The green belt developed via this approach addresses issues such as urban sprawl and also provides recreational

areas. On the other hand, a bottom-up approach is followed by communities or local organizations. This approach promotes sustainable practices and fulfil specific needs of the community. Besides these, sometimes hybrid approaches are followed considering both the top-down and bottom-up approaches for development of a green belt area. In this approach, designing and establishment of area is done following bottom-up approach but the basic framework is based on top-down approach. A combination of bottom-up and top-down approaches for development of green areas is recommended by experts for holistic development (Macdonald et al., 2021). Development of a multipurpose energy-green belt is trending nowadays. This area provides biomass for fuel generation or other purposes, preserves soil, improves air quality and also proves useful in combating environmental issues such as desertification, land degradation, floods and water shortage. This type of multi-dimensional approach is being followed in some countries of the world (Alherbawi et al., 2022; Kirby et al., 2024).

In India, the development of green belt areas is mandatory for industrial zones. The green belt in these areas and other zones need to be developed following the guidelines given by Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) and Forest Department. These organizations work under the supervision of Ministry of Environment Forests and Climate Change (MoEFCC). Green belt of width 200m to 500m is suggested for mega industries and other pollutant emitting sources depending on space availability (Kumar et al., 2019). Specifications given by the Forest department and municipal corporations for development of green belts in different areas has been given in Table 2.

Table 2. Specifications for green belt in various areas/zones.

Type of areas	Specifications for green belt
Mining areas	7.5m wide
	2500 plants per ha
	Plants should have survival rate of about 80%
Industrial areas	33 % area of total area
	local species planted near the boundary of the plot
Construction sites	Vegetation should cover the peripheral regions of the plot. Indigenous plant varieties should be grown.
Hazardous waste disposal sites	33% of the total area
	Native species planted along the boundary
	10m wide
Manufacturing plants	three tiers of plantation of native species
Roadside	shrub height 1 to 1.5 m
	tree height 3 to 5 m
	Trees and shrubs planted together for high density and uniform foliage

The performance of the green belt area is dependent upon factors such as height and canopy of trees, distance between species, and density of plants. Climatic factors such as wind velocity, topography of the land, size of land, amount of pollution, characteristics of soil and water also affect the functioning of GB areas.

Global status of green belts

Studies conducted in Canada and Germany show that the greenbelt has a vast territorial scope and the new policy for green belt development aims at multifaceted goals including protection of farmland, environmentally sensitive areas, providing recreational spaces and mitigating and adapting to climate change. Studies from Ontario and Frankfurt demonstrate that new-generation greenbelts require different institutional structures to enable their effective governance. The research related to designing of multi-purpose green belts in vulnerable coastal areas is been conducted in several countries. The studies focus on developing green areas that can help in reduction of disaster risks. The Greenbelt Plan is framed with the coordination of policy makers and conservationists in conjunction with municipalities and the federal government. Thus, the Greenbelt Plan at present is a multifaceted plan related to conservation of nature, management of resources, ecological functions and economic perspectives. Vision for GB areas in arid lands is related to water resources management, reclamation of damaged or polluted soils and maintenance of ecological functions with vision for the green belt (Alherbawi et al., 2022; Zuniga-Teran et al., 2022).

Countries like India are planning to create a long (about 1500Km) and wide (about 5 Km) green belt extending from the western part of the country and extending till the extreme north. The development of this green Wall is to limit the land degradation and expansion (towards east) of the

Thar desert. A similar plan named 'Great Green Wall' project extending from Senegal (West) to Djibouti (East) was developed by Africa in 2007. Another green belt is being planned from Porbandar to Panipat (Fig. 1). This is being developed with an aim to restore degraded land via afforestation along the Aravali hill range. India targets for restoration of about 26 million hectares (mha) of the land via green area programme.

Fig. 1. Picture showing development of great green wall from Haryana to Gujarat (Courtesy: Google images).

Disadvantages of green belt

Besides having many advantages, some limitations in development of green belt include availability of land around source of pollution particularly in countries like India. Studies have shown that green belt development puts a strain on rural infrastructure such as roads and other utility networks which might already be operating at full capacity. Moreover, it can reduce the availability of surfaces for drainage setups. Proper maintenance of green belt is very crucial to get the desired result of pollution abatement and maintenance of other ecosystem services within the project area for a longer duration.

Conclusion

Green belt is an area used for mitigation of air pollutants, noise, and use of treated wastewater. Other benefits like addition to aesthetic value, climatic amelioration, biomass generation, and enhancement of biodiversity have also been noted in these patches of green areas. The plant species used in these areas mainly include fast growing, tolerant tree and shrubs trees with high potential to absorb pollutants and restore soil fertility. These areas need to be developed according to the guidelines provided by authorities to get maximum benefits. Specifications for green belt vary for every region depending upon the area (industrial or residential zones). The green belt areas in and around urban and industrial areas play a crucial role in maintaining the ecological health of the region by providing ecosystem services and achieving environmental sustainability. Moreover, they safeguard environmental threats. Thus, green belt areas can prove beneficial in addressing the current environmental issues. The development of these green areas needs to be emphasized for a sustainable future.

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